

ABOUT INCREASING THE ENDURANCE OF YOUNG ATHLETES

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Annotation: in each sport, the endurance aspect is of great importance and it assumes that special attention should be paid to the development of this physical quality. The article will talk about improving the quality of endurance of young athletes, their control and assessment.

Keywords: endurance, Physical Culture, Sports, category of athletes, methods of increasing endurance, loading, speed.

Endurance is the ability of a person to perform any activity of movement for a long time without reducing its effectiveness. Various methods for developing the quality of endurance in sports practice have been recommended by a number of scientists. Including flat, repeated, interval, variable, circuit, race methods.

In an even way, there is an opportunity to give a load, taking into account the individual physical fitness of students, and make it easy to daze on time. In this method, the exercises are performed at a single pace and promote the development of general endurance.

The repeated method allows you to control the load during sufficient rest intervals, with the number of repetitions. The interval method clearly regulates the time to perform the exercise and recover.

The variable method, on the other hand, involves performing exercises at a variable pace, depending on the size of the load, with a rest interval of 1-1.5 to 3-4 minutes, depending on the training, with an endurance of 140-180 beats/min.

The circular method, general physical fitness (UJT), allows different means of special physical fitness (MJT) and their combinations to be applied in a variety of ways.

The method of competition is effective in improving the leading physical qualities inherent in the chosen sport in a sharp conflict activity with an opponent.

It is known that loadings with an agile nature create favorable physiological conditions for loadings that require greater manifestation of endurance. They, on the other hand, leave a "mark" on the performance of the agility exercise for several hours after it (if there was a serious increase), which negatively affects the performance. For Example, K.Cooper noted that the high level of overall endurance, in particular among American players, contributes to an increase in competitive activity in the second half of the game and at the end of the season, as well as a decrease in the number of injuries. However, it is also not appropriate to overestimate the effect of total endurance on the manifestation of another type of endurance [1, B. 224].

Researcher M.Ya. Nibatnikova by general endurance refers to the ability of an athlete to perform any physical work (load) for a long time, which includes many muscle groups and has a positive effect on his specialization in sports, while special endurance takes time based on

the requirements of the athlete's specialty. tishi.ma lum believes that it is the ability to effectively perform a download [2, B. 261].

It has also been found that speed loads harmonize well with effects with strength characteristics, in which a positive continuous effect can apply under certain conditions, that is, both in the case when strength training is performed before speed training, and in the case of their reverse sequence.

For the successful implementation of the work of training young athletes, it is necessary to carefully take into account the age features of development, the level of training, the features of the chosen sport, the peculiarities of the development of physical qualities, the formation of movement skills and qualifications.

The knowledge of the age zones of the trainer allows you to better systematize the multi-year training process. However, age is not the only factor that is necessary to consider when building a rational system of many years of training. It is necessary to thoroughly study the individual physical abilities of athletes, the most favorable periods for the education of physical qualities, as well as the predisposition to qualitatively master technical and tactical activities.

In youth, a reserve of all physical abilities becomes available. To do this, rational and regular pedagogical influences should be encouraged. Pedagogical impact on the development of the physical abilities of young athletes the growth in one step or another of the age-appropriate development process contributes to the full manifestation of the most vividly expressed abilities.

With the use of low-intensity aerobic loads, the results achieved with extremely intense loads, which lead to excessive strain of physiological activities, can also be achieved with the help of optimal means for the body. It is susceptible to the effects of sluggish intense exercise, which develops endurance, especially children 8-10 years old. At the age of 12 to 15 years, the samadoriality of these exercises decreases, the endurance stabilizes or slightly decreases.

The secret of physiologically based tools that develop endurance in children and adolescents includes various types of cyclic exercises that increase the aerobic productivity of the body. In this respect, it has become known that moderate-strength running (at the limit of about 60% of the maximum), the duration of which is gradually increased, is preferable to other exercises. For this purpose, it is recommended to include action games and game exercises in training.

When tests are carried out on the duration of speed walks at 75% of the maximum, the greatest increase in endurance is observed in boys at 13-14 years old, and in girls at 10-13 years old. In addition to the low-speed running during the Wsmirlik period, a fast-paced run of 400-500m (for boys) and 200-300m (for girls) is used. The weekly volume of running is increased to 35-45 km.

The main requirement for physical exercises aimed at the development of general endurance in childhood and adolescence is to create a gentle, attentive mode of training on the ground of high emotional lifting. The fulfillment of this requirement is a necessary condition for supporting interest in training in young athletes, as well as the emergence of conditions for further specialization. In the conditions of school sports clubs before the era of Wsmirlik, a physiological foundation for the upbringing of special endurance appears.

Children and adolescents with an average level of physical development adapt faster to physical loads aimed at growing endurance. In school students with a high level of physical development, the performance in performing speed and agility – strength exercises will be higher than in their peers with a moderate or low level of physical development.

Favorable morphological and functional conditions for the development of endurance occur at the age of 9 - 10 years. In boys, hypersensitivity to dynamic strength exercises will consist of 2 periods: from 9 to 10-12 years old and from 14 to 17 years old. Ke-lib strength endurance in girls 11 years old reaches the indicators of girls 15-16 years old. In students 7-10 years old, stagnant voltages are accompanied by the rapid development of exhaustion. In schools, physical education classes of grades 5-8 are successfully used such as dynamic strength exercises with small weights (1-2 kg), climbing a rope, carrying a load, ironing a cast - iron ball. In connection with an increase in strength endurance at the age of 15-16, the number of exercises performed with weights of 2-3 kg increases, time-out on the rope, elements of struggle are applied. Strength training in girls of this age is limited due to a decrease in relative muscle strength. In training with adolescents, it is necessary to use exercises that require stagnant situations, initial states, hanging and leaning.

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